

DESCRIPTION OF INDIVIDUALISM VERSUS SOCIALISM IN JACK LONDON'S 'MARTIN EDEN'

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ANNOTATION: This article gives information about one of masterpiece works of J. London called 'Martin Eden' and individualism and socialism in the novel is discussed.

KEY WORDS: individualism, novel, society, socialism.

Jack London is considered one of America's best writers. His literary works are an inexhaustible source of inspiration for millions of readers around the world. London is a scholar of human psychology, and all of his characters undergo remarkable personal transformations. Martin Eden, one of Jack London's most famous novels, is no exception to this rule. In it, the evolution of the main character can be observed: from his life in the courtyard of working-class neighborhoods to the young man's great popularity at social events. Martin Eden is a hymn to human will, self-improvement and rational stubbornness. Although London himself does not provide such information, some literary critics consider Martin Eden to be a novel containing autobiographical elements. The following paper traces and analyzes the autobiographical elements used by Jack London in the novel through the prism of his official biography. The reader first meets Martin Eden, the main character of the novel, when he replaces Ruth Morse. It can be seen that Martin is a shabbily dressed man with an awkward demeanor. London describes Eden using the following words: "She was dressed in rough clothes that beat the sea, and she was out of place in the spacious hall in which she found herself." suits the sophisticated atmosphere of the place. Later, man learns about the origin of Eden. He is a former

sailor from a poor family. Like every ambitious young man, he wants to make a name for himself, but doesn't know how. Like his character, Jack London comes from a working-class family. His father, Marshall Wellman, was one of the first settlers in the Massachusetts Bay Colony (Wellman, 1918), a builder. Although Wellman was a down-to-earth person, London's mother, Flora, was a learned woman who took a serious interest in the spiritual development of her children. Perhaps his mother instilled in the future writer a desire for new knowledge and self-improvement. So both Eden and London have the same background. Both men were born into poor families; but they chose a life markedly different from that of the members of their class. They believe that self-education and continuous self-improvement are the most effective means of avoiding constant need and want. Both people strive to realize themselves in the literary field. Although London's and Eden's motivations are vastly different, their ultimate goal of self-improvement is similar. Both believed that their literary vocation was to proclaim the greatness of the working people and to destroy the boundaries between classes. As he gradually climbs the popular social ladder, Martin Eden does everything he can to help his peers, whom poverty and destitution have forced them into submission. Like his main character, London is known as an outspoken opponent of class oppression and an active participant in the struggle for equality. The words London used to close all his letters, "Yours for the Revolution," illustrate this point very well. ²¹ Both Martin Eden's life and Jack London's ended tragically. Men died at the height of their lives, at the height of their writing, professional and personal achievements. Eden's love for Ruth Morse was not to be a happy story. At the beginning of the novel, the young man thinks that his writing career and his subsequent strong financial position are the trump cards that will help him win the favor of a young lady.

Martin Eden commits suicide, and this is the price of his success. Unlike his protagonist, Jack dies in his bed at the London Winery cottage. Although all his biographers agree that the writer's death was caused by an overdose of morphine,

they argue whether it was an accident or not. Today it is impossible to find the truth, but there is a striking similarity between the fates of both men. The life of Jack London and the life of his hero, Martin Eden, exemplify the idea that success does not come alone, but comes with heartache and sorrow. Despite the tragic end of both men's lives, you can't tell this is a story of personal failure. True, both men sacrificed their lives measured by their loved ones. In fact, having both men is associated with physical and emotional pain. Perhaps the price they paid for their dream was too high, but all their efforts were not in vain. Although London and Eden could not be happy themselves, they were able to bring happiness to the people around them. Their lives have become a source of inspiration for thousands of young people who strive to improve themselves and live in a free and harmonious society; and this is perhaps the most important similarity between London and Eden. Martin Eden is a 1909 novel by the once famous American writer Jack London, which tells the story of a young man struggling to gain recognition among the literary elite of his time. The social stereotypes and cultural contrasts of his life and times hate the relationship between the poor and the bourgeois rich class, which forms one of the struggles that young Martin fights, especially given that he falls in love with Roth Morse; a young bourgeois woman from a well-to-do family. This work is a reimagining of a masterpiece by a true literary craftsman, which explores the day-to-day challenges faced by struggling young writers in getting their work published. In London's literary ingenuity, Mark Eden is staged in such a way that it is seen as a living autobiography for Jack London himself, from the similarity of various themes and postulates in the book with the author's own views during his life; In fact, the issues discussed in the book are so close to London's view of life that even the tragic ending of Mark Eden's suicide has been reasonably assumed to represent Jack London's death. Mark Eden tries to explain the plot of the book by trying to find out how the author's life is reflected in the book. The essay also examines various topics discussed in the book and compares them with the ideological views of the author

during his life. In addition, the essay aims to determine whether there is anything autobiographical in the book about the author's life. These goals are achieved by quoting and inferring from the book to substantiate the postulates and confirm the assumptions made in this regard. Further corroborating comments from various authorities and literature on the same topic are also used to strengthen the credibility of the findings and conclusions herein. This book is a favorite among aspiring writers who are faced with the reality of the challenges of publishing their literary works. It is the story of the young and brave Martin Eden, who, with his determination, fought to earn a living for himself through self-education in the early 20th century and later to gain control of the literary elite. As the story unfolds, it becomes clear that Eden's hard work and desire to make a name for herself among society's elite is Ruth Morse's love. Social stereotypes and social norms sweetly deny the possibility of Eden's alliance with Ruth, because they are from two different social classes: Eden is from the lower working class of sailors, and Ruth is from the upper bourgeois class.

In order for Eden to make some effort to achieve one of his dreams of living happily and living an honorable life with Ruth, he must establish himself as a writer, his lifelong dream, hence his passionate attempts to publish his work. This is Martin Eden's first close-up of the life of Jack London. Martin Eden's skepticism about publishers and publishers is the same nonsense that London viewed publishers as a struggling writer in his formative years. Indeed, there is no better way to fully understand London's disgruntled cynicism than in Eden's words: "Eden assumed that there was no human being in the guise of an editor who would receive his manuscripts when he sent them, but on the contrary, any manuscripts taken from this envelope would automatically be stamped with another stamp changed and then returned them to the sender(s) with a well-written rejection slip."

There are authorities who have reasonably speculated that the character Ruth Morse was modeled after Jack London's first love, Mabel Applegarth, who as a

young writer had always rejected her for her "failure" in life. In this regard, there is also a direct deduction from the life of London, which is closely related to Martin Eden, which may justify the argument that the book has autobiographical tendencies. Nevertheless, there are significant differences in the story that are not at all consistent with London's beliefs of his time. The issue of socialism and individualism described in the book is an example of this. From the book, Eden rejects socialism as "slavery" and instead welcomes individualism based on Nietzsche's ideology. London, on the other hand, wrote to Upton Sinclair about discrediting individualism, saying in his correspondence: "One of the greatest motives in the book was a masterful attack on individualism, which I think I have not yet been corrupted by. One reviewer of this book discovered it".

The book ends tragically with Adan committing suicide by drowning. This happened at his best moments, when he received recognition and his writing received wide recognition, which means that he should have the highest satisfaction that he was going to achieve such success in life. Once he reached the height of his literary genius, society itself turned upside down, as it meant that even his enormous success as a writer failed to gain him recognition. nobility and upper social class. There was always resentment and hatred of his contemporary artists from the social class, something that drove Eden mad. This continued disrespect eventually led him to commit suicide. In Jack London's Martin Eden, the theme of individualism versus socialism is explored through the protagonist's struggle to find his place in society. Martin, a young sailor eager for knowledge and eager for success, is torn between his individual aspirations and the socialist ideals of Ruth, his love interest. Throughout the novel, Martin's individualistic mindset is portrayed as both a strength and a weakness. On the one hand, his determination and hard work lead him to success as a writer, allowing him to achieve his dreams of wealth and fame. On the other hand, his individuality leads him to reject the socialist values of his peers, which leads to his loneliness and isolation.

In contrast, Ruth represents the socialist ideals of community and equality. He believed that people should work together for the greater good of society rather than pursuing their individual desires. However, Martin tries to reconcile his love for Ruth with his own individual ambitions, and as a result, their relationship fizzles out. Ultimately, the novel shows that both individualism and socialism have advantages and disadvantages. While individualism can lead to personal success and satisfaction, it can also lead to isolation and a lack of connection with others. Likewise, while socialism promotes community and equality, it can also stifle individual creativity and ambition. In conclusion, "Martin Eden" explores the tension between individualism and socialism through the eyes of its protagonist. Through Martin's journey, the novel highlights the strengths and weaknesses of both ideologies, and ultimately the reader decides which path is best for them.

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